

Research Article

Green Human Resource Management in Conjunction with the Sustainability of Corporate Environments

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A B S T R A C T

Recently, there has been an experienced increase in the level of awareness among business groups about the relevance of becoming green and implementing different approaches for environmental management. Provisions such as green personnel, green professions, green occupations are becoming more commonplace in the present world. The business world is becoming more globalized, concurrently, the business is undergoing a transition from an outdated financial structure to a contemporary capacity-based economy that is green to investigate the environmentally responsible parts of the organization's operations. The "green revolution" also known as "going green", "ecological protection" or "environmental sustainability", "sustainable standard of living", "caring for our earth", a number of other similar concepts, have evolved into natural phenomena that are easily visible in our day-to-day lives. At the present time, Green Human Resource Management, also known as GHRM, has developed into a vital business strategy for big corporations. This is the case in companies where the Human Resource Departments take an active role in making the workplace more environmentally friendly. This paper focuses primarily on the numerous green human resource policies and practices with corporate environmental sustainability and data obtained from secondary accessible sources. It provides an explanation of the essential functions that next-level thinking of a new population of people plays in terms of green technology and knowledge. In addition to this, the study contributes to the existing body of literature by addressing the trajectory of the development of various environmentally green functions. In conclusion, the paper presents a few potentially fruitful HR initiatives that green businesses should use to rescue both the environment and people.

Keywords: Green Human Resource Management, Sustainability of Corporate Environments, Eco-Friendly, Green Revolution

Introduction

The transition toward industrialization, which leads to growth in business output, technology, other business activities, is one of the primary drivers of contemporary living across the world. It is not only a growth in human sustainability but also an increase in its level of life in the world, despite the fact that it is the result of increases in ecological dangers to the activities of human beings. Therefore, at this time, people need to make use of environmentally green practices in order to safeguard the environment of the world as well as the most non-renewable resources of the planet and human. We want green from construction to humans (Mishra and Rai, 2017).¹² Leading is all about creating hope and making the workforce dedicated towards optimal performance (Mishra, 2018).¹⁰ Mishra (2019) emphasised value management as an investment in the brain which results in a gain, however investments in cash may sometimes crash and the leading organizations are focusing on HR to avoid constraints for growth and development (Mishra, 2020).^{8,9} Green human resource management seems to be the pioneering notion for the majority of academics and professionals working in the field of human resource management (Ali. M.C et al.,2020).² It started in 1996, when author Wehrmeyer (1996), who wrote a book called "Greening People: Human Resources and Environmental Management," became involved.¹⁸ The 21st century has seen a rise in interest in environmental issues all over the globe, even though these issues are not directly related to any other sectors, such as public affairs, political affairs, or business. The Kyoto Protocol in 1997, the Bali Protocol in 2007, the Copenhagen Accord in 2009 are three examples of particular climate change accords that have contributed to the current surge in interest in environmentalism throughout the world. Because of the negative effects that industrial pollution and waste materials, such as toxic chemicals, have on people and society as a whole, governments and Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs) all over the world have promoted rules and policies that have the effect of slowing down and, to some extent, even reversing the depletion of natural resources and the ill effects that this has on human beings and society as a whole.

In light of the current circumstances, the organizations have the additional responsibility of identifying means and procedures for addressing a decrease in their ecological footprints in addition to addressing economic difficulties. To achieve success within the corporate community list of priorities of the leaders of the corporate world in the business world as the awareness of incorporating green into the corporate strategy is making its way in business, but still, the topic is not comfortable with the majority of practitioners working in the HR environment.

When it comes to the execution of any corporate environmental program, various divisions within an organization, such as HR, Marketing, Information Technology, Finance, etc., work together to put forth a positive effort. The human resource management division, however, is the most significant source among these various divisions. Without a shadow of a question, the corporate world is a big player in the discussion about environmental problems, as a result, it should be considered a vital component of the solution to the environmental threat. There is compelling evidence that in the world of business, a significant portion of the workforce force has a proactive sense of empowerment regarding the environment. This is because employees in today's world are more dedicated to and content with organizations that actively promote green practices. Within the last two decades, there has been a convergence toward a universal or worldwide consensus about the need for proactive practices and methods of environmental management.

Review of Literature

According to Yang, Lin, Chan, Sheu (2010), who said that sustainability shows that an increasing number of HR executives are eager to modify their organization as such to become exclusive environmental champions, the phrase "more and more HR executives are keen to" The influence of environmental management practices on the performance of an organization has been the subject of a significant amount of empirical study, this research has focused on a variety of performance indicators.¹⁹

According to Zoogah (2011), the writer explained that Green HRM is the use of HRM policies, beliefs, practices to promote the sustainable use of company resources and to prevent any unfavourable effects emerging from environmental issues in business.¹⁷

According to Jackson et al., (2011), the writer explained that Green HRM is an emerging where researchers have started to describe the connection between HRM functions and environment management. The future direction for the researchers is to link the strategic HRM perspective and environmental management.⁶

According to Jabbour and Jabbour (2015), the concept of green human resource management is connected to the HRM function as the primary driver of green initiatives in an organization. This was explained in further depth in the article.²⁰

According to Mehta and Mehta (2017), the author explained how to implement environmentally friendly HR practices and procedures for the sustainable use of resources.

According to Beck-Krala and Klimkiewicz (2017), Green Human Resource Management is a component of sustainable human resource management that focuses on

producing evaluation for business stakeholders during an instant consideration for efficiency, social, environmental elements in HR activities.²¹

Objective of the Study

The main purpose of this study is to investigate the overarching notion of environmentally responsible management of human resources in conjunction with business’s environment and potential resources for long-term sustainability.

Methodology

The secondary focus of the study focuses on primarily collected information. The present body of literature was assembled using a variety of resources, including online databases and printed publications. An ordered evaluation of the amassed body of literature was carried out in a painstakingly specific manner. A reference has been equipped from Mishra, 2018.

Green Human Resource Management

Green human resource management is the most penitential of policies to encourage the sustainable use of resources inside businesses and, more often, advances the causes of environmental sustainability. GHRM is directly responsible for developing green personnel that investigate, appreciate, practice green plans and maintain its green objectives throughout the HRM process of recruiting, hiring, training, compensating, developing, advancing the enterprises of human capital. GHRM is directly responsible for developing green personnel that look into, appreciate, practice green plans. It is a reference to the policies, practices, systems that constitute the workforce force of the green association for the benefit of the individual, society, natural environment, as well as the benefit of the business organization.

Green Practices

It is possible to be environmentally responsible, cost-effective, practical all at the same time by embracing “green practices.” To maintain your green status, you may choose from a variety of eco-friendly solutions.

Table I.Environment Solution for Green HRM

Green Environmentally-Friendly	
Green Printing	Energy Efficient Office Spaces
Green Manufacturing and Disposal of Staff ID card	Green Payroll
Job sharing (sharing a full-time job between two employees)	Car Pooling
Teleconferencing and virtual interviews	Public Transport

Recycling of waste materials	Company Transport
Telecommuting	Flexi-Work
Online Training	e-filing
Encouraging cycling to work	Reduce employee carbon footprints by the likes of electronic filling; Green HR involves reducing carbon footprint via less printing of paper, video conferencing and interviews, etc.
Car Sharing	
Electronic Voting Machine	
Carbon Credit Card	

Source: Compiled secondary data from Google

Sustainability

It is common practice to describe sustainability as “the capacity to meet the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs.” This idea has now expanded to incorporate all types of social as well as environmental impacts, going beyond the notion of environmental sustainability. Employers are going to need to come up with a new method of doing business as more and more companies make sustainability a primary emphasis of their operations. When it comes to making choices about their operations, sustainable businesses need to pay attention not just to the bottom line but also to the effects their actions will have on society and the environment.

Corporetal Environmental Responsibility

Customer environmental responsibility is another name for the Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) initiative, which focuses on both social and environmental concerns. The stakeholder CSR theory proposed by Freemans in 1999 resources an emphasis on problems relating to human rights and the global environment, as well as on actions that are connected to human resource management practices. The environment of environmental corporate social responsibility promotes the notion that the conservation of natural resources should go hand in hand with the functioning of a business. The function of HRM in gaining an understanding of CSR is important, both CSR and HRM are vital to gaining an understanding of the dynamic that exists between employers and workers. Researchers can explore a range of policies since the majority of corporations are employing their large resources to guarantee that their corporate social responsibility practices make the company socially accountable. Take, for example, the

force of the sun and the wind. Stay ahead of the impacts of global warming caused by humans. Policies to guarantee that the environment of the planet does not continue to deteriorate to the point those future generations are forced to deal with water shortages, harsh weather occurrences, excessive temperature.

the awareness of the company's approach reaches its zenith. The problems that are included in green overall performance administration are those that are connected to the environmental concerns and insurance policies of the company.

Figure 1. Green Customer Environmental Responsibility and Human Resources

Green Human Resource Management Functions Future Direction

The Green House Regeneration Manifesto (GHRM) is a document that assists in the development of green individuals inside a company that can comprehend and value green living. This kind of environmentally inexperienced endeavour can keep its environmentally inexperienced objectives all through the HRM technique of recruiting, hiring and coaching, compensating, growing, advancing the company's human resources. A corporation's Human Resource Department can play a substantial role in the development of a sustainability culture inside the organization thanks to the department's effective efforts.

Green Recruitment

In the "war for talent," a primary human resources venture is to attract remarkable bodies of workers. According to the research on employee turnover and retention, the most essential benefit factors of human resource management and long-term sustainability are employee retention or recruitment, as well as employee satisfaction.

Green Overall Performance Management

Performance management is the procedure of encouraging personnel of an organization's workforce to develop their organizational skills in a manner that contributes more effectively to the organization's achievement of its goals and objectives. The PM is the point at which

Green Training and Development

Training and development is an improvement that focuses on improving the skills, knowledge, attitudes of workers while also preventing the decline of EM-related knowledge, skills, attitudes. Green education and improvement are processes that teach personnel about the value of EM, instruct them in working strategies that conserve energy and reduce waste, spread environmental consciousness throughout the organization, grant opportunities for personnel to participate in the resolution of environmental issues.

Green Compensation

The most important HRM strategies for recognizing and rewarding personnel for their achievements are monetary rewards and other forms of performance. These HR practices are the most effective technique that hyperlinks together an individual's activity with that of the organization.

Green Worker Relation

The relationship of HRM known as employee members of the family is concerned with the worker of cordial organizing relationships between employers and employees. The relationship improves the motivation and morale of the staff, as well as the staff's ability to perform effectively and efficiently. In its most basic form, worker members of the family are comprised of worker participation and empowerment activities.

Green Building

In place of conventional workplaces, businesses all over the business are thinking about the possibility of relocating to environmentally inexperienced buildings that may serve both as their headquarters and their workplaces. The phenomena are very influential in terms of defining new trends since green structures adhere to construction standards that aim to reduce the number of natural sources that are used throughout the building process.

Paperless Office

Even though the vast majority of the work in the workplace is still handled using paper, the amount of paper used has decreased because of the development of statistical technology. Today, e-commerce and increased levels of education have brought about changes in the methods and approaches used in workplaces, transforming them into paperless offices. A paperless workplace is a location of the business in which the use of paper is both restricted and eliminated. This is accomplished by digitizing critical and respectable archives as well as other materials, which are then included in automated work processes.

Conservation of Energy

Power conservation at the workplace has the potential to have a significant environmental effect on the surrounding environment. In an attempt to provide more environmentally friendly and eco-friendly services, workplaces all over the globe have implemented a variety of environmental conservation efforts to supply their environmental effect. It is believed that HR structures such as e-HR will be able to aid management and personnel in monitoring their carbon emissions.

Recycling and waste disposal

The practice of converting spent substances, such as waste, into new items that may be valuable to society is referred to as recycling. The process of recycling cuts down on the number of raw substances that would have been utilized in its place if new items had been manufactured. Several organizations are making recycling programs mandatory as part of their efforts to reduce their green impact and increase the number of recycled goods produced while simultaneously cutting down on the amount of waste produced. To protect the environment, the whole company world is now repeating the present-old mantra of the "three Rs," which includes reduction, reuse, recycling.

Health and Safety

The employee's health and safety should be focused through a systematic plan by investigating possible hazards and welfare facilities under a sound strategy and working conditions (Mishra et al, 2022: Mishra et al, 2019: Adhikari et al, 2020: Mishra and Aithal, 2021: Adhikari et al, 2022: Lama et al, 2019).

Religion as Means for Environmental Safety

It is not a new concept to link anything with religion which needs care (Mishra, 2022). It can be illustrated through the case of Swargdawari Dham, Janakpur, Nepal an initiative of Hon. Pawan Singhania. He has just converted the most polluted place into the cleanest place by establishing the temple of lord Shiva. A place where people used to be buried or burnt after death was highly polluted on the bank of the pond. As for local people, they used to be afraid to travel along the way. He just argued this is the last moment for the body on the earth which needs to be cleaned and he used religion as means through the establishment of lord Shiva Temple. Now, it is a tourist place where people take photos and create videos through TikTok and many more. He himself established as president of the last item. This could be further developed as a source of green finance also (Mishra and Aithal, 2022).

Conclusion

Any technology that wishes to evolve sustainably must prioritize technological development. If these environmental problems are going to be solved without putting mankind back in the technology of abject destitution, then there is an absolute need for the development of new technologies. The fact that a company's human resources are its most valuable asset is no longer a closely guarded secret. Human resources play a crucial role in the resource of personnel; therefore, an organization cannot exist without them. At this company, because there is a growing trend among businesses to concentrate their attention on greening their operations, modern HR managers have been given the additional business of incorporating the Green HR philosophy including mission assertion along with HR policies. This has come about as a direct result of the current trend. Changes in the perspectives of the company that are associated with environmental initiatives can be observed in written coverage statements, environmental job titles, advertising and marketing strategies, capital investments, auditing practices, new product sketches and development, manufacturing procedures. Procedures and policies that adhere to environmentally friendly practices are gradually finding their way into the HR sector to supplement the existing non-environmentally friendly practices and efforts. Efforts made in the area of green human resources have led to increased efficiency, decreased prices, increased worker retention, doubled levels of productivity, among other concrete advantages. It adopts environmentally inexperienced HR practices, with a special focus on waste management, recycling, reducing the company's carbon footprint, as well as the use of and production of environmentally conscious goods. It is evident that the majority of the staff personnel care deeply about the

environment and, as a result, demonstrate a greater level of commitment and work pride towards an organization that is ever prepared to become green. The Greening of HRM involves specific HR insurance policies and practices that are connected with the three sustainability pillars-environmental balance, social harmony, monetary parity. The responsibility that falls on the shoulders of the current generations of HR managers is to bring the concept of green HRM to the attention of the younger generations as well as the employees who are currently working for the organization. Green actions such as the usage of herbal resources and assisting the company in maintaining an environment that is desired and preserving herbal sources for our future period are examples of sustainable development. Last but not least, human resources have a significant opportunity to contribute to the organization's green movement and play an essential role in energizing, supporting, inspiring personnel to adopt environmentally friendly practices for greener business.

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References

1. Adhakari R, Mishra AK, Joshi KR. Causative factor of accidents in commercial buildings of Bharatpur Metropolitan City. *Saudi J Civ Eng* 2020; 4(7): 101-12. DOI:10.36348/sjce.2020.v04i07.001
2. Ali MC, Islam KMA, Chung SJ, Zayed NM et al. A Study of Green Human Resources Management (GHRM) and Green Creativity for Human Resources Professionals. *International Journal of Business and Management Future* 2020; 4(2): 57-67.
3. Pardhi A, Chaudhari A. Importance of Green Human Resource Management. *The International journal of analytical and experimental modal analysis* 12, 0886-9367.
4. Bangwal D, Tiwari P. Green HRM-A way to greening the environment. *Journal of Business and Management (IOSR-JBM)* 2015; 17(12): 45-53.
5. Bombiak E, Green human resource management- the latest trend or strategic necessity? *Entrepreneurship and Sustainability Issues*, 2019; 6(4): 2345-0282.
6. Jackson SE, Renwick DWS, Jabbour CJC. State-of -the -Art and Future Directions for Green Human Resource Management: Introduction to the Special Issue. *German Journal of Human Resource Management: Zeitschrift Für Personal forschung* 2011; 25(2): 99-116.
7. Lama C, Sah DP, Mishra AK. Occupational Hazards Identification and their RiskAssessment during the Construction of Head Race Tunnel in Middle Bhotekoshi HydroelectricProject. *International Journal of Research - Granthaalayah* 2019; 7(3): 227248. <https://doi.org/10.29121/granthaalayah.v7.i3.2019.965>
8. Mishra A. Implementation Status of Value Management in Project Management Practicein Nepal. *International Journal of Management Studies* 2019; 6(1): 92-108.
9. Mishra AK. Implication of Theory of Constraints in Project Management. *International Journal of Advanced Trends in Engineering and Technology* 2020; 5(1): 1-13.
10. Mishra AK. Assessment of Human Resource Capacity of Construction Companies in Nepal. *Journal of Advanced Research in HR and Organizational Management* 5(4): 2018; 14-25.
11. Mishra AK. & Singh, NK. A Review on Time and Cost Issues of Infrastructure Projects. *JAdvRes Const Urban Arch* 2018; 3(1&2): 32-46 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7066243>
12. Mishra AK, Rai S. Comparative performance assessmentof eco-friendly buildings and conventional buildings ofKathmandu valley. *International Journal of CurrentResearch* 2017; 9(12): 62958-62973.
13. Mishra AK, Adhikari R, Aithal P. Linkage of Safety Site Conditionswith Accidents. *International Journal of Health Sciences and Pharmacy (IJHSP)* 6(1): 17-34. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6325770>
14. Mishra AK, Lama C, Sah DP. Effectiveness Assessment of Preventive and ControlMeasures of Safety Implementation. *J Adv Res Civil Envi Engr* 2019; 6(2): 1-20. DOI:<https://doi.org/10.24321/2393.8307.201903>
15. Mishra AK. Aithal PS. Job Safety Analysis during Tunnel Construction. *International Journal of Applied Engineering and Management Letters (IJAE ML)* 5(1): 80-96. DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4842501>
16. Mishra AK, Aithal PS. An Imperative on Green Financing in the Perspective of Nepal. *International Journal of Applied Engineering and Management Letters (IJAEML)* 2022; 6(2): 242-253. ISSN: 2581-7000. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7221741> Crossref DOI: <https://doi.org/10.47992/IJAEML.2581.7000.0155>
17. Mishra AK. A Reference Book on Comparative Assessment from the Eastern Approach. Zenodo 2022. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7113124>
18. Tubsi P, Yunho Ji. A conceptual approach to GHRM and corporate environmental sustainability in the hospitality industry. *Journal of Asian Finance, Economics and business* 7(1): 2288-4637: 2288-4645.
19. Zoogah DB. The dynamics of green HRM behaviors: A cognitive social information processing approach, *German Journal of Human Resource Management* 2011; 25(2): 117-139.
20. Wehrmeyer WEd. Greening People: Human Resources